

YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA UCHINCHI RENESSANS RIVOJIDA JADID ILM-FANINING TUTGAN O'RNI.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada jadid bobolarimizning jamiyatni rivojlantirish maqsadida olib borgan sayh-harakatlari, davlatimizda olib borilatotgan islohotlar haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Renessans, uyg'onish, sivilizatsiya, strategiya, innovatsiya, islohot.*

THE ROLE OF MODERN SCIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE THIRD RENAISSANCE IN NEW UZBEKISTAN.

Abstract. This article talks about the efforts of our ancestors for the development of the society and the reforms that can be carried out in our country.

Key words: *Renaissance, awakening, civilization, strategy, innovation, reform.*

РОЛЬ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ В РАЗВИТИИ ТРЕТЬЕГО РЕНЕССАНСА В НОВОМ УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассказывается о усилиях наших предков по развитию общества и о реформах, которые можно провести в нашей стране.

Ключевые слова: *Возрождение, пробуждение, цивилизация, стратегия, инновации, реформы.*

XIX asr oxiri va XX asr boshlarida bir qator sharq va musulmon mamlakatlarida vujudga kelgan jadidchilik harakati Turkiston o'lkasida teran tarixiy ildizlarga egadir.

Yurtimiz ulkan ijtimoiy-siyosiy va ma'rifiy ahamiyatga ega ushbu jarayonlardan chetda qolmagani, aksincha, bu harakatning markazlaridan biriga aylanganini ta'kidlash lozim. "O'z zamonining ilg'or namoyandalari bo'lgan jadidlar g'oyat murakkab va qiyin sharoitda bilim va ma'rifat tarqatish, ta'lim- tarbiya sohasini tubdan isloh etish orqali milliy taraqqiyotga erishish g'oyasi bilan maydonga chiqdilar. Xalq koriga yaragan, xalqqa xizmati singan buyuk insonlarning nomlari doimo xalqimizning xotirasida mangu bo'lishi tabiiy hol. Yillar o'tsa ham bunday kishilarning qilgan ishlari ibrat va namuna sifatida ko'rsatilaveradi.

XIX asr oxiri-XX asrning boshlarida Turkistonda chor mustamlakachiligining kuchayishi natijasida Markaziy Osiyoda jadidchilik harakati kuchayib ketdi. Jadidlar- (arabcha "jadid" so'zidan olingan bo'lib "yangi" degan ma'noni bildiradi).

Turkiston xalqining boy ijtimoiy-falsafiy, diniy-axloqiy, madaniy taraqqiyotida XIX asrning birinchi choragidagi davr o'zining nihoyatda sermazmun va inqilobiy suronliligi, g'oyaviy-nazariy va mafkuraviy harakat shakllarining xilma-xilligi bilan ajralib turadi. Bu holat ijtimoiy taraqqiyotning o'ziga xos yo'nalishi edi. Turkiston XIX asrning ikkinchi yarmida Rossiya tomonidan bosib olindi va mustamlakaga aylantirildi. Turkistonda mustaqillik, milliy taraqqiyot uchun, xalqning manfaatlari uchun kurash olib borishga milliy-ozodlik harakati uchun zamin tayyorlashga muvaffaq bo'ldilar. Yerli xalqlar orasida mustamlakachilikka qarshi ma'rifatchilik g'oyalari tarqala boshladi, yangi ta'lim-tarbiya shaxobchalari, yangi maktab, maorif, madaniy targibot, jadidchilik harakati rivoj topdi. Mana shunday sharoitda Turkistonda ko'plab ma'rifatchilar yetishib chiqdi. Behbudiy, Fitrat, Cho'lpon, Abdulla Qodiriy, Abdulla Avloniy, Munavvarqori, Fayzullo Xo'jayev, So'fizoda, Tavallo, Ishoqjon Ibrat kabilar g'oyat og'ir sharoitlarda targ'ib etishga harakat qilganlar. Ular millatning kamolotini yuksaltirish, uning qadriyatini yerga urishga yo'l qo'ymaslik borasida katta ishlar qilganlar. Ma'rifatchi jadidchilar og'ir moddiy qiyinchiliklar, g'oyaviysiyosiy tazyiqlarga qaramay, millatning ma'naviy yuksalishi uchun imkoniyatlar yaratishga harakat qildilar.

«Bu ulug' zotlarning maqsadi — jaholat va qoloqlik girdobida qolib kelayotgan Turkiston xalqini dunyoviy ilm-fan, ilg'or kasb-hunarlar bilan qurollantirib, umumbashariy rivojlanish yo'liga olib chiqishdan iborat edi. Jadidlar tomonidan tashkil etilgan yangi usuldagi maktablar, teatr, kutubxona va muzeylar, gazeta va jurnallar, Turkiston farzandlarini chet ellarga o'qishga yuborish maqsadida tuzilgan xayriya jamiyatlari xalqimizni necha asrlik g'aflat uyqusidan uyg'otdi, milliy ozodlik harakati uchun beqiyos kuch berdi».

«Afsuski, yurtimizda bolsheviklar diktaturasi o'rnatilgani, chor mustamlakachilik siyosati yangicha shaklda davom ettirilgani ma'rifatparvar bobolarimizga o'z maqsad-muddoalarini to'liq amalga oshirish imkonini bermadi. Lekin ularning ezgu orzu-niyatlari xalqimizning qon-qonida, tarixiy xotirasida saqlanib qoldi va hanuz yashamoqda, desak, ayni haqiqatni aytgan bo'lamiz».

«Bugungi kunda butun xalqimizning qalbidan chuqur joy olgan, umummilliy harakatga aylanib borayotgan „Yangi O'zbekiston“ g'oyasi zamirida ana shunday ulug' ajdodlarimiz, umuman olganda, milliy tariximizda Birinchi va Ikkinchi uyg'onish davrlariga asos solgan alloma bobolarimizning orzu-intilishlari va armonlari ham mujassam, desak, adashmagan bo'lamiz».

Biz chuqur anglab yetamizki yuksak ma'naviyatli avlodgina Uchinchi Renessansning bunyodkori bo'la oladi. Buning uchun ularning ongi va qalbiga "Renessans" tushunchasining mazmun-mohiyatini va Uchinchi Renessans milliy g'oyaga aylanishi zarurligini hamda yoshlarda mafkuraviy immunitetni tarbiyalashga xizmat qilishini singdirib borishimiz zarur.

Haqiqatan tarixan olganda biz ikki Renessansni boshdan kechirdik: birinchisi IX-XII asrlar, ikkinchisi XIV-XVI asr. Birinchi Renessansda yurtimizdan Farg‘oniy, Xorazmiy, Forobiy, Beruniy, Ibn Sino, Yusuf Xos Hojib, Mahmud Qoshg‘ariy, Mahmud Zamaxshariy kabi buyuk daholar, buyuk muhaddislar – Buxoriy, Termiziy, mutakallimlar – Moturidiy va Abul Muin Nasafiy hamda boshqa atoqli dunyoviy va diniy allomalar shuuri olamni yoritdi.

Ikkinchi Renessansda – Ulug‘bek, G‘iyosiddin Jamshid Koshiy, Qozizoda Rumiy, Ali Qushchi, Lutfiy, Jomiy, Navoiy, Behzod, buyuk me‘morlar, bastakorlar, musavvirlar, tarixchilar chiqib, bugun ham dunyoni lol qoldirayotgan asarlar yaratdilar. Har ikki Renessans davrida biz dunyoning ilg‘or, mutaraqqiy xalqlari qatorida edik. Agar yana shunday darajaga erishmoqchi bo‘lsak, Uchinchi Renessansni amalga oshirmog‘imiz zarur.

Uchinchi Renessans g‘oyasini, avvalo, jamiyatimiz chuqur anglab olmog‘i kerak. Har jabhada, sohada qiladigan ishlarimiz, rejayu istiqbol dasturlarimiz, ta‘lim- tarbiya va kadrlar siyosati, investitsion siyosat – barchasi unga sharoit va muhit yaratishga qaratilmog‘i lozim.

“Biz Uchinchi Renessans masalasini strategik vazifa sifatida oldimizga qo‘yib, uni milliy g‘oya darajasiga ko‘tarmoqdamiz. Biz maktabgacha talim va maktab talimi, oliy va o‘rta maxsus talim tizimi hamda ilmiy-madaniy muassasalarni bo‘lg‘usi Renessansning to‘rt uzviy halqasi, deb bilamiz. Bog‘cha tarbiyachisi, maktab muallimi, professor-o‘qituvchilar va ilmiy-ijodiy ziyolilarimizni esa yangi Uyg‘onish davrining to‘rt tayanch ustuni, deb hisoblaymiz.

Men ishonaman – hurmatli ota-onalar bu tashabbusni albatta qo‘llab-quvvatlab, yangi Renessansning beshinchi halqasi, beshinchi ustuni bo‘ladilar”-, deb ta‘kidladilar Prezidentimiz.

Bosh vazifamiz esa Uchinchi Renessansning mustahkam poydevorini yaratadigan yosh avlodni yuksak ma‘naviyatli insonlar qilib tarbiyalashga qaratilishi lozim. Uchinchi Renessans milliy g‘oyaga aylanishi zarur va yoshlarda mafkuraviy imunitetni tarbiyalashga xizmat qilishi kerak. “2022-2026 yillarga mo‘ljallangan “Yangi O‘zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi”da belgilab berilgan maqsadlarida, Yoshlarni vatanparvarlik, fuqarolik tuyg‘usi, bag‘rikenglik, qonunlarga, milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarga hurmat ruhida, zararli ta’sirlar va oqimlarga qarshi tura oladigan, hayotga bo‘lgan qat‘iy ishonch va qarashlarga ega shaxs sifatida tarbiyalash, yoshlarni axloqiy negizlarni buzishga olib keladigan hatti-harakatlardan, terrorism va diniy ekstremizm, separatizm, fundamentalizm, zo‘ravonlik va shafqatsizlik g‘oyalaridan himoya qilish, ya‘ni xavfsizlik, millatlararo totuvlik va diniy bag‘rikenglikni ta‘minlash, chuqur o‘ylangan, o‘zaro manfaatli va amaliy ruhdagi tashqi siyosat yuritishga yo‘naltirilgan davlatimiz mustaqilligi va suverenitetini mustahkamlash, O‘zbekistonning yon-atrofida xavfsizlik, barqarorlik va ahil qo‘shnichilik muhitini shakllantirish, mamlakatimizning xalqaro nufuzini mustahkamlashni nazarda tutadi.

O'zbekistonda bugun jadallik bilan kechayotgan ana shunday islohotlar, jamiyatdagi yangilanishlar mamlakatda kezayotgan uyg'onish ruhidan dalolatdir.

Uchinchi Renessans uzoq istiqbol masalasi emas. U bugun, ushbu onda jamiyatimiz, uning har bir jabhasida muttasil etilib kelayotgan real voqelikdir. Ishonchimiz komilki, yurtimizda boshlangan bu yangilanishlar izchil davom etadi va xalqimiz orzu qilgan buyuk davlat, farovon kelajak, barpo etishda mustahkam poydevor barpo etadi.

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